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and Reuse of Heritage**

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Circular approach for deep renovation of historic building heritage. The case of a manor villa in Argelato, Bologna

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Abstract: Buildings are responsible for about 40% of the European energy consumption and 36% of greenhouse gas emissions from energy. As stated by the European Renovation Wave, effective actions - both at the policy-legislative and academic and corporate research level – are crucial to making Europe climate-neutral by 2050. In this framework, the “DRIVE 0” European Horizon 2020 project is aimed at developing innovative solutions for energy refurbishing the existing buildings, based on a circular approach. The circular solutions developed in cooperation between universities and factories are intended to be prototyped and implemented in real pilot cases in order to test their feasibility. This paper presents the specific Italian demo case located in Argelato, constituted of a manor villa included in the “Corte Palazzo” building complex. Two different envelope solutions – a traditional ETICS system and an innovative Plug&Play solution - are applied to the building in order to compare their circularity. The results of the analyses, which consider not only the Embodied Energy and Embodied CO₂, but also parameters linked to the Design for Disassembly, Materials Origin, and Re-Usability of materials and components, bring out some important reflections on the actual lack of application of a circular approach to historic buildings.

Keywords: Circularity, historic buildings, deep renovation, environmental impact, circularity indicators

1. Introduction

The Horizon 2020 European project “DRIVE 0 - Driving decarbonisation of the EU building stock by enhancing a consumer centred and locally based circular renovation process” (G.A. no. 841850) [1] deals with the promotion of decarbonisation strategies of the existing building stock through the implementation of deep renovation interventions. The project intends to encourage the adoption of a circular approach within the renovation processes that, in order to be attractive and effective, must be based on the actual needs of the end-user. According to the DRIVE 0 approach, circular renovation is based on the use of energy from renewable sources and the use of materials from biological or technical cycles, in which waste production is minimised and end-of-life strategies with a positive impact on the environment (*Cradle to Cradle*) are envisaged [2]. The project, in which the Department of Architecture of the University of Bologna (UNIBO) is involved in carrying out the present research, identified several case studies located in the partners' home countries on which to apply a deep renovation intervention based on the implementation of circular strategies. Among these cases, UNIBO contributed with a demo case located in Argelato (Bologna, Italy), owned by a private foundation.

After a critical analysis of the building, the paper presents a description of the interventions that are currently underway, whose project was developed by the study commissioned by the foundation in cooperation with UNIBO with the aim of renovating the building complex according to the adoption of an approach that is as circular as possible. In particular, the building envelope was analysed in-depth, through the performance of Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) and analysis of circularity indicators defined in the framework of DRIVE 0 [3], aimed at identifying circular intervention strategies. The principle of circularity pursued is based on the promotion of the use of local materials, the reuse of existing materials, and the installation - where possible - of Plug&Play, prefabricated, and dry-assembly building components with reduced environmental impact throughout their life cycle.

2. Description of the case study

The Italian demo case is located in Argelato, a small Municipality near Bologna. It consists of a building complex constructed in the early 1900s and partially demolished and rebuilt over the decades, composed of a manor villa, a hayloft/stables, and a small animal shelter (Figures 1, 2). In 2021, when the private foundation decided to intervene in the building complex, it was compromised and damaged in terms of seismic safety, architectural and conservative quality, and energy and mechanical performances. In fact, the residential complex has been abandoned for so many decades. It needed deep renovation interventions to adapt the spaces to new current functions and make them again habitable and comfortable. At the end of the renovation process, the Municipality of Argelato will dispose of the renovated “Corte Palazzo” building complex: while the manor villa will be transformed into a multi-user social residence for disadvantaged families and disabled people, the former barn-stable will host social services for the use of residents and citizens, surrounded by a park of great landscape value.

Figure 1. (Left) Aerial photo of the building complex located in a garden of ecological importance, constituted of a hayloft/stables and a manor villa (© 2020, Mazzoli, C.), and (right) zoom on the two street fronts of the buildings (© 2020, Cioni, M.).

The buildings are subjected to a historical-documentary constraint, and the regulations in force (the Urban Planning Regulation *RUE – Regolamento urbanistico Edilizio* of Argelato, Bologna, art. 20 [4]) do not allow for deeply intervene on façades, but just on the roof. In particular, given the historical-documentary constraints on these buildings, the regulations allow realising a “*Restoration and conservative renovation of type A (RC-A)*” on the manor villa (that is classified as building “A2” for the RUE), with the possibility of using the entire recoverable surface area within the building outline and in compliance with the conditions of eligibility in respect of the type of intervention.

Figure 2. External view of the villa (left) and the hayloft/stables (right) (© 2020, Mazzoli, C.).

A procedure for verifying the presence of an additional architectural constraint on the building complex (Legislative Decree no. 42 of 22/01/2004 [5]) was developed and, in October 2020, it gave the following outcome: the villa and the hayloft are not subjected to an architectural constraint, and therefore it is possible to softly intervene on the façade and on the other architectural elements. However, it is mandatory to preserve the typological-constructive characters of the buildings by realising interventions that do not alter the historical-testimonial character of the buildings. Furthermore, the complex is inserted within a park extended for 1.20 ha that is protected as a garden of ecological importance. This issue represents another important boundary condition to be considered for the design of the renovation interventions.

This paper is focused on the manor villa, representing the Italian pilot case selected by the DRIVE 0 project (Figure 3). The manor villa consists of a load-bearing masonry building in solid bricks. A brief description is provided below for all building components to highlight the before-intervention state of the building, in terms of construction elements description and conservation conditions, and with reference to the high seismicity of the Italian territory.

Figure 3. 3D model representing the current state of the villa: cross-section (left) and longitudinal section (right) (© 2020, Habitat Plus).

The foundation is composed of load-bearing masonry in solid common bricks jointed with mortar, and it presents a thickness of 50 cm and a depth of 40 cm. The diagnostic analysis developed showed that the conservation of the foundation and its dimensions are not even adequate for the safety of the building at the current stage: therefore, it was necessary to integrate the foundation with compatible brick materials in order to increase its dimensional extension and its mechanical performances.

The external walls are constituted of load-bearing masonry in solid common bricks jointed with mortar (two layers of bricks for a 29 cm of total thickness), externally finished with a coat in lime-based plaster and a finishing paint coat, and internally with a coat in gypsum

plaster. The mechanical analysis showed that the external walls were not even adequate for the safety of the building at the current stage; therefore, it was necessary to integrate them with compatible brick materials in order to increase their dimensional extension and mechanical performances. Furthermore, the addition of an external thermal insulating layer was necessary to meet the regulatory energy requirements. The same integration intervention was also implemented for the internal load-bearing partitions.

The ground floor slab and the internal floor slab between the ground and first level are composed of unidirectional floor slabs in steel beams IPE 160 and hollow bricks (*volterrane*) for lightning. The internal floor slab between the first and second levels is composed of a unidirectional floor with wooden primary and secondary beams. The wooden floor slabs were partially destroyed, and in general, all the slabs were very damaged (Figure 4); therefore, all the slabs were reconstructed in the absent portions and were reinforced in order to guarantee seismic safety. It is important to note that the structural elements had to be preserved since the building is subject to a historical-documentary constraint.

The roof frame was composed of wooden beams and joists, on which a layer of hollow tiles was placed, covered by a wooden planking layer and then by traditional imbrex ceramic tiles. The state of conservation of the roof was completely compromised in terms of structural performance, seismic safety, thermally insulating, and waterproofing terms. The analyses showed that it was necessary to completely remanufacture it. However, due to the historical-documentary constraint, shape and dimensions had to be preserved, and so the new construction system had to use materials compatible with the original structure.

Figure 4. Internal views of the wooden roof structure and floor slabs (© 2020, Mazzoli, C.).

3. Deep renovation intervention

The Italian pilot represents a typical rural residential commonly widespread in different rural territories of Southern Europe and Italy. This specific case study represents an example of renovation and refurbishment of historical buildings, fostering a cycle of requalification of this architectural typology according to a circular approach, which is completely innovative in the field of protected heritage. The interventions concern the implementation of reconstruction and renovation interventions through the reuse of original materials and new sustainable and partially prefabricated components. Indeed, the existing and territorial construction materials are reused, respecting the traditional and regional architectural standards. After the retrofit, this rural building stock will meet a high level of energy efficiency based on the circular use of materials

and building components with high technological solutions for energy efficiency improvement (Figure 5).

Figure 5. Renderings of the executive design project of the villa: the building complex (left), the East façade (middle), and the West-South view of the villa (right) (© 2021, Habitat Plus).

Once all permits were obtained, the construction works began in July 2021, and the end of the works is scheduled for the mid of 2023. Due to the Covid-19 pandemic, there have been some significant delays, especially in the process of obtaining permits from local authorities to carry out the intervention on the protected building complex and in the obtainment of raw materials and products. This deep-renovation demonstrator is based on the circular actions described below.

The four-pitched roof was totally reconstructed. The prefab circular solution originally planned was based on the innovative technology consisting of prefab modular panels with a structural wooden frame and different wooden thermal insulating layers. Unfortunately, it was not possible to realise the originally planned system because of the significant economic barriers consequently to the Covid-19 pandemic situation and the ministerial incentive measure *Superbonus 110%* [6] that, starting from May 2020, enormously inflated prices in the construction sector and considerably lengthened delivery times. Hence, the roof was rebuilt using a construction technique similar to the original one, through a wooden structure and on-site thermal insulation layers in glass wool (24 cm) and external high-density wood fibre (4 cm). Furthermore, 90% of the original ceramic roof tiles has been reused in the new roof, thus reducing the environmental and economic impact of the deep renovation intervention. Photovoltaics (PV) panels will be installed on the South oriented portion of the roof. The PV panels will be integrated into the building roof to respect the constraints of compatibility of the interventions with the original historical system.

Regarding the opaque building envelope, after a deep structural reinforcement of the external load-bearing walls, the four façades will be refurbished by implementing the different systems. For the South and East oriented façades, a traditional External Thermal Insulation Composite System (ETICS) in EPS (20 cm thickness) will be implemented, fixed and glued to the existing façades. An innovative façade technology designed by an Italian local factory will be implemented on the North and West oriented façades: it consists of 2D Plug&Play prefab panels, filled in with an internal glass wool layer and an external sandwich panel in rock wool, for a total thickness of 20 cm, equal to that of the ETICS used for the other façades. The adoption of prefabricated components in the field of protected building heritage is very complex: it must be compatible with the existing context (after a precise laser scanning metric survey) and fit in coherently with it, also from a construction point of view, in accordance with the requirements of the authorising entities. The implementation of two different solutions – one traditional and the other more innovative - allowing to achieve the same thermal transmittance value ($0.19 \text{ W/m}^2\text{K}$), according to legislation, is aimed at testing the technical feasibility and energy performance of the two solutions (Figure 6).

Regarding the transparent building envelope, the new windows will be integrated within thermal insulated prefabricated frames (*monoblocchi*), which also include the related window shading systems.

Figure 6. Design project of the façades of the villa: East and South façades (top) and West and North façades (down) (© 2021, Habitat Plus).

4. Circularity assessment

The concept of Circular Economy (CE) has been evolving since the 1970s when the idea of *Regenerative Design* was introduced by the American Professor John Tillman Lyle [7]. Subsequently, other schools of thought were born, up to the concept of *Cradle to Cradle* proposed in 2002 by Michael Braungart and William McDonough [8], which proposes a way of designing products that have a positive impact on the environment. These schools of thought are often based on the idea of creating an economic model similar to biological cycles. It must be specified that these models tend to simplify a concept in order to create new positive habits in the industrial economic system, and, for this reason, they cannot reach the actual complexity of real biological systems.

The reliability of a model is based on its ability to best describe the phenomenon being analysed, making appropriate simplification operations that do not distort its meaning. The transition to the CE is led by the multidisciplinary corporation Ellen MacArthur Foundation, which published a series of reports to promote and spread the application of the CE. It states that a CE “is based on the principles of designing out waste and pollution, keeping products and materials in use, and regenerating natural systems”. [9] The CE is an industrial and economic model that proposes a regenerative and restorative design. Its scope is to redefine products and services and design

them with the aim of keeping them in the circle of usability. In other words, the objective is to eliminate the “waste” phase of the linear economy and keep the product alive as long as possible in order to completely eliminate the waste and minimise negative impacts on the environment and the consumption of raw materials. Therefore, it is of fundamental importance to tend towards this direction as much as possible and try to develop the technologies and know-how to really achieve this goal or get there as close as possible.

In this chapter, a circularity analysis - both quantitative and qualitative - is presented, taking into account all these aspects, with reference to the four different façade solutions analysed for the building under study (Figure 7).

4.1. LCA Analysis

Within the framework of DRIVE 0, the assessment of Embodied Energy (EE) and Embodied Carbon (EC) values is developed through the compilation of the Material Passport, which contains the list of all materials and components constituting the building, classified according to Brand’s “6S” theory, i.e. the 6 layers (from the most to the least durable): Site, Structure, Skin, Services, Space Plan, Stuff [10]. Each material is associated with an EE and EC value, taken from Hammond’s Inventory of Carbon & Energy (ICE) database [11], which considers the impacts during the *Cradle to Gate* process, i.e. from the moment the raw materials are extracted until they leave the factory.

However, in this paper, the results obtained from a more in-depth - albeit simplified - LCA analysis carried out through the use of *OneClick LCA* software are presented in order to assess the environmental impact of the four different envelope solutions considered for energy refurbishing the building (Tables 1, 2).

The results are expressed according to the different categories of the impact that the product generates in the various environmental sectors. In this particular case, two parameters have been considered:

- the EC, which represents the Global Warming Potential (GWP), that is the increase in the anthropic greenhouse effect, measured on the basis of the number of emissions of CO₂eq in the atmosphere generated by the consumption of energy and materials;
- the EE, which represents the use of primary energy expressed in MJ, including all the direct and indirect energy used to transform the raw materials in the product.

Figure 7. Stratigraphy of the four façade solutions analysed (© 2022, Mazzoli, C.).

Table 1. *Plug&Play façade solutions: list of materials/components and related quantity per functional units*

Plug&Play demo		Plug&Play original	
Resource (from inside to outside)	Quantity [kg/m ²]	Resource (from inside to outside)	Quantity [kg/m ²]
Glass wool insulation (120 mm)	2.29	Glass wool insulation (120 mm)	2.29
Sandwich panel in rock wool (80 mm)	17.50	Sandwich panel in rock wool (80 mm)	17.50
Fiber cement board	16.90	Steel brackets	2.42
Steel brackets	2.42	Cladding in gres porcelain tails	24.00
Gypsum plaster	2.25	Aluminium structure (80% secondary and 20% primary)	2.49
External finishing	1.60		
Total	42.96		48.70

Table 2. *ETICS façade solutions: list of materials/components and related quantity per functional units*

ETICS demo		ETICS original	
Resource (from inside to outside)	Quantity [kg/m ²]	Resource (from inside to outside)	Quantity [kg/m ²]
Adhesive cementitious layer	11.32	Adhesive cementitious layer	7.26
EPS insulation (200 mm)	3.50	EPS insulation (200 mm)	3.50
Steel brackets	0.19	Steel brackets	0.16
Fiber glass mesh	0.18	Fiber glass mesh	0.16
Plastic disk dowel (Fischer type)	0.05	Plastic disk dowel (Fischer type)	0.05
Gypsum plaster	2.55	Primer coat	0.13
External finishing	1.60	External acrylic finishing layer	1.28
Total	19.39	Total	12.54

OneClick LCA allows seeing the impacts divided by phases of the life cycle, by material, and by categories of the building, producing graphs that allow an immediate reading of the result, in order to see which resource has the major contribution to the impact.

The results reported below regard the analysis of a functional unit (1 m²) of façade surface, during the whole life cycle, from the extraction of materials until the 25 years of the life of the building: A1-A3 Materials; A4 Transportation; A4-leg2 Transportation leg 2; A5 Construction; B1-B5 Maintenance and replacement; B6 Energy; B7 Water; C1-C4 End of life.

Table 3. *Use of Primary Energy (EE) [MJ] in the life different phases for the analysed façade solutions*

Façade solution	A1-A3	A4	A4- leg2	A5	B1-B5	B6	B7	C1-C4	Total EE
Plug&Play demo	787.00	13.10	-	-	6.74	-	-	11.50	818.34
Plug&Play original	1,360.00	16.80	-	-	-	314.00	-	5.58	1,696.38
ETICS demo	263.00	5.65	-	-	28.40	-	-	7.17	304.22
ETICS original	247.00	4.67	-	-	62.40	-	-	6.28	320.35

In terms of EE, the two ETICS solutions are quite equivalent to each other, producing less than one third of the energy compared to the prefabricated solution (*Plug&Play demo*). Comparing the two prefabricated solutions, on the other hand, the originally designed circular solution (*Plug&Play original*) turns out to be significantly more impactful than *Plug&Play demo*, both considering the initial phase A1-A3, as well as considering the entire life cycle. Maintenance and replacement phases B1-B5 are, of course, only present in the two demo solutions, as the other two originals have maintenance times exceeding 25 years. On a larger scale, considering

a longer period, this would imply benefits on the environmental impact of more prefabricated façade systems.

Table 4. Global Warming Potential (EC) [$\text{kgCO}_2\text{eq/m}^2$] in the life different phases for the analysed façade solutions

Façade solution	A1-A3	A4	A4-leg2	A5	B1-B5	B6	B7	C1-C4	Total EC
Plug&Play demo	70.90	0.46	-	-	4.66	-	-	1.13	77.15
Plug&Play original	101.00	0.60	-	-	-	18.80	-	0.38	120.78
ETICS demo	19.10	0.20	-	-	5.94	-	-	9.38	34.62
ETICS original	15.70	0.17	-	-	2.90	-	-	9.32	28.09

In terms of EC, the two ETICS solutions are less impactful than the prefabricated solutions and, among them, the more impactful one is the *ETICS demo* since it includes a gypsum plaster and a lime-plaster external finishing consistent to the original one. Among the two Plug&Play solutions, on the contrary, considering phases A1-A3, the prefabricated solution actually applied to the case study (*Plug&Play demo*) presents a lower impact compared to the prefab solution (*Plug&Play original*) which was originally designed but was not applicable due to the constraints to which the historic building is subjected. However, when considering phases B1-B5, the *Plug&Play original* system does not require maintenance (phases B1-B5) over a 25-year life span and therefore, considering a longer life span, it can be assumed that for Plug&Play systems the CO₂ emitted in phases A1-A3 is amortised by the reduced CO₂ emissions in phases B1-B5.

In conclusion, when analysing EE and EC values, prefabricated circular solutions are more impactful than traditional ETICS solutions. However, as mentioned earlier, this paper also wants to put focus on the other aspects of circularity, which are explained in the next section.

4.2. Potential for reuse and recycling of materials and waste

Within the framework of DRIVE 0, the term “circularity” does not only refer to environmental impact in terms of Embodied Energy (EE) and Embodied Carbon (EC) values, but also to other criteria. In line with what was developed within the framework of DRIVE 0 [12], based on extensive research in the literature [13], UNIBO developed a simplified method to quickly assess the level of circularity of a building component or an entire building, by an overall numerical index, which was obtained by means of certain circularity parameters. This is not the context to explain in-depth the methodology developed by UNIBO, called “EASY- Express ASsessing tool for CircularityY” [14]. It is sufficient to know that this methodology was conceived with the aim of simplifying the assessment of the level of circularity of interventions on existing buildings, where - contrarily to what happens in new constructions - it is not possible to know the Environmental Product Declarations (EPD) or a similar certification of environmental impact for each material used. By identifying a Building Circularity Indicator (BCI), the method can provide an easily understandable and accessible tool for all operators involved in the building process.

For the identification of a single overall circularity indicator, it is necessary to identify a set of parameters that are actually meaningful for the assessment of circularity. The starting point for the selection of relevant criteria developed by DRIVE 0 is based on “LEVEL(s)”, the European framework for sustainable buildings [15]. In particular, the most relevant for DRIVE 0 is macro-objective 2 “Resource-efficient and circular material cycles”. From these and other significant contributions, a set of parameters for the circularity analysis were selected and defined, which can be grouped into three categories:

- i) Design for Disassembly (DfD): measures the disassembly capacity of a product, derived from four of the numerous criteria proposed by Alba Concept [16] and van Schaik [17]: type of connections; accessibility of connections; overlaps; form containment. These four parameters are related to the conformation and demountability of construction elements and the average of their values can be considered as a single DfD parameter that identifies, precisely, the product's ability to be disassembled. The closer the parameter is to 1, the easier the product is to disassemble.
- ii) Materials Origin (MO): provides an overview of the origin of the materials, products, and components used. It is intended to attribute a weighted value referring to the source of origin of the material examined. The parameter can be chosen from various options: material already in use, present in the analysed building; locally repaired material, reused materials and components; reconditioned/recycled material; virgin material of organic origin; virgin material of inorganic origin. The closer the parameter is to 1, the more circular the material is as it has a high percentage of reused or recycled material.
- iii) Re-Usability (RU): represents a fundamental aspect that indicates the potential for reuse of materials at the end of their life. Again, this is a parameter introduced to promote the choice of products that are as reusable as possible and to discourage, on the other hand, the choice of products with low circularity. The closer the parameter is to 1, the greater the ability of the material to be readapted for future use.

For each of these parameters, a value is assigned ranging from 0 (zero degree of circularity) to 1 (maximum degree of circularity), which is then weighted by formulas to arrive at the EBCI.

It is evident that the *Plug&Play original* solution, analysed in terms of these parameters, is the one with the highest degree of prefabrication and reversibility and therefore the highest level of circularity. In fact, this solution provides a first layer of glass wool insulation, fixed by dowels, followed by a layer of rock wool sandwich panels anchored by steel brackets to the existing façade, and covered by a ceramic cladding system anchored to an aluminium substructure. All components are dry-assembled and, in case of repair or replacement, are easily accessible and removable (DfD value close to 1). Each component already includes a percentage of recycled material: the rock wool, the glass wool of the sandwiches, and the aluminium of the substructure (MO value close to 1). At the end of its life, each component can be reused or recycled again, thus reducing the environmental impact of the building envelope (OR value close to 1). According to the parameters identified in DRIVE 0, this prefab solution is highly circular but, unfortunately, it was not applicable due to the historic-documentary constraint which imposed the use of the original lime-based plaster as the finishing layer.

Finally, some considerations were made from the point of view of waste generation and the possibility of reuse of the materials constituting the façade systems at the end of their life. ETICS systems cannot be recycled as they are assembled using an adhesive layer in addition to mechanical anchors. This implies some critical issues regarding the selective disposal of the components and therefore their reuse. On the other hand, the *Plug&Play* systems, which have a high level of circularity in terms of DfD and MO, are highly circular in terms of waste. In fact, as can be seen from the table below, for the latter there is a percentage of reusable material. When comparing the two systems, the *Plug&Play original* system, with its recyclable ceramic cladding and metallic structure and anchoring, produces almost half as much waste as the *Plug&Play demo* system, with its non-recyclable lime-based plaster finish. So, in terms of waste, the *Plug&Play original* system also has less impact on the environment.

The issues related to waste and recovering potentials of materials and components are crucial in relation to the new Circular Economic Action Plan (CEAP) adopted by the European Commission, whose objective is also to ensure that waste is prevented, and the resources used are kept in the EU economy for as long as possible [18]. Based on the analyses conducted, it is possible to definitely assess that the *Plug&Play* systems are more circular than traditional ETICS systems.

Table 5. Percentages of recyclable material at the end of life for the two prefabricated solutions

Façade solution	Waste	Reusable materials
Plug&Play demo	95.35%	4.65%
Plug&Play original	40.63%	59.36%

5. Results and conclusions

The analysis developed is focused not only on the EE and EC values but also on the other parameters that have been considered in DRIVE 0 to assess the level of circularity of a construction system. In the academic context, further research activities are still in progress to reach an even better degree of precision for assessing the level of circularity in all its facets. In this framework, UNIBO is also working to contribute to this purpose. In particular, the above-mentioned methodology for easily assessing the level of circularity is currently under development, thanks to the cooperation between the partners and factories involved in the project.

Based on the results obtained, it can therefore be said that a comprehensive analysis of all circularity parameters is crucial to raising awareness and understanding how to contribute to decarbonisation in the building sector. It is important that this awareness is spread at all levels, from the customer who must make the final decisions to the designer who develops the project and the regulatory institutions that define the laws and authorise the projects. This specific case of the historic villa in Argelato, which represents a large part of the highly consolidated built context in Italy, shows that the regulatory framework is often a major obstacle to the diffusion of highly circular innovative technological solutions that could contribute to decarbonisation. The legislative constraints attributed to the existing buildings, especially those with architectural and historic-documentary interest, represent a significant barrier to the adoption of a circular approach to deep renovation interventions.

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